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CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE: EVIDENCE FROM NIGERIA

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Abstract

More than ever in the economic history of Nigeria, there is a greater need for good corporate social responsibility. The present crises are too many to attempt to exhaust in this article: gender inequality, lack of sufficient art and culture education, poor communities, low donations and gifts, poor health and safety, customers' complaints, data protection and privacy issues, poor human rights, low impact assessment, poor product quality, etc. There is a general acceptance of the need for corporations to intervene in providing essential services that can help people. However, the big question is what is in it for these corporations? In this paper, efforts are made to determine this and many more questions. The research design is correlational with a population and sample of 156 and 112, respectively. Four filters were applied: corporations listed with the Nigerian Exchange Group as at the end of 2021 were considered; companies without complete 10 years annual reports were excluded, corporations that were quoted after 2021 were excluded and firms with technical difficulties with the Exchange as indicated on its website were excluded. The total quoted corporations that were used was 112 for a period of 10 years which produces 1,120 observations. The dependent variable which proxy financial performance was an index derived from return on assets, earnings per share and return on equity. The independent variable: corporate social responsibility is treated as an index derived from human resource, environmental activities, community donations, gifts and new product research and development. In the case of control variables, we employ firm size and leverage. Following the results of the model, *p*-values, *t*-values, *R*², *Prob* > *F* value, we report that corporate social responsibility is positively and significantly related to corporate financial performance. We drop leverage in favour of firm size because of the model specification error test results, though it is negatively insignificant.

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INTRODUCTION

Firm financial performance (FFP) has been varyingly interrogated by scholars (; Yahaya et al., 2015; Yahaya, 2018). However, because of its continued relevance, researchers cannot be said to over flog it. FFP is a measure of how well a corporation uses its financial and non-financial resources to generate revenues (income). It is very important to organisations because it tells about its general well-being. It is a snapshot of its financial health and it is a proxy of managements' effectiveness. It provides insight to the future, that is, it determines whether its operations are on track or not. Therefore, monitoring FFP creates stability and confidence in managers to take both short- and long-term

decisions. Financial performance is a symptom of sound health and business growth financier as it equips the organization to out run competitors who may not measure up in this regard.

It is a comprehensive examination of a firm's standing in assets, liabilities, equity, expenses and revenues management or utilization. In a way, it refers to the extent to which financial objectives are achieved by the corporation. However, it should be noted that not all organizations are in business to make profit; some are simply non-profit driven otherwise properly known as non-governmental organizations (NGOs). It is necessary to state clearly at this stage that the scope of this article does not cover NGOs. Therefore, financial performance is treated in this paper to include firms whose main goal is to make money. It also must be said at the onset that more money enables businesses to share in societal responsibilities. This is the very principle behind linking corporate social responsibility with financial performance, the very theme of this paper. It also means that good corporate social responsibility is good for financial performance because stakeholders will patronize the business.

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is a form of organization's self-regulation designed to contribute to community objectives of a philanthropic or charitable nature through engaging in volunteer services or ethically oriented activities. It is the degree to which organizations are socially responsible for providing legal, ethical and both financial and economic moral standards. In another expression, it is the belief that corporations need to take active responsibility for societal lives. It implies that corporations have social responsibility even when meeting their profit goals. CSR is synonymous with corporate citizenship (CC). Therefore, in the remaining part of this article, we will be referring CC as CSR. CC or CSR is seen in this paper as corporate interventions in the areas of human resource development, environment, community donations and gifts, and new product research and development.

Human resource development activities include activities such as equal employment opportunities, workforce incidents and accidents, employee gender diversity, employments for indigenous people, etc. Environment programs cover materials, wastes, energy, water, biodiversity, emissions, carbons, effluents, regulatory compliance and impact assessment. Also, community activities consist of donations and gifts, and health, safety, education, arts, cultural sponsorships, and human rights activities. New product research and development activities are designed to take care of customers and their complaints. It also covers investments designed to protect consumers from data and privacy breaches.

The purpose of this paper, therefore, is to interrogate the impact that corporate social responsibility has on financial performance of quoted firms operating in Nigeria. The paper is motivated by the need for corporations to complement or supplement existing government efforts in the areas of human resource empowerment activities, environment, local communities and new product R&D. The study offers both policy and performance improvement opportunities. In this regard, the findings are different from past studies and it will extend the frontier of knowledge and provides a foundation for further research. The remaining sections of the article include literature review, hypotheses, methods, findings and conclusion.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

Investigations connecting corporate social responsibility with financial performance have produced four broad findings: those that are significantly positive, those that are significantly negative on one hand and those that are insignificantly positive and insignificantly negative on the other hand. As a consequence, the empirical literature will be presented and reviewed based on these classifications or typologies. The next paragraphs consist of empirical studies that indicated significant and positive impact of CSR on FFP.

Tsoutoura (2004) explored the relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance of S&P-500 firms over 1996-2000. The results indicated that it is positive and statistically significant. Pelozo and Papania (2008) examined the relationship between corporate social responsibility and firm financial performance. They reported a significant and positive association between the two variables. Also, Jackson and Parsa (2009) presented a model that encapsulates a firm's financial performance and its performance relative to CSR initiatives. They proposed four quadrants: black for companies that did well in achieving financial performance; green for firms that its objective is not profit but CSR; blue for corporations that did well at both CSR and FFP; and yellow for companies that underperform in both initiatives. They reported that corporations under their consideration were all blue, that is, they found significant positive association between CSR and FFP. Note that the study failed to indicate the sector, population and sample size of the study. Also, Peters and Mullen (2009) used time series data to empirically analyze the effects of CSR on firm financial performance. The evidence was that CSR had positive and significant effect on FFP. Nelling and Webb (2009) examined the causal relation between corporate social responsibility and financial

performance. They reported that the two variables are positively related. Kapoor and Sandhu (2010) examined the impact of CSR on CFP in terms of profitability after controlling for the impact of firm growth of 93 corporations in India for the period 2005-2006. The results indicated significant and positive impact of CSR on profitability. Note that probability is a measure off financial performance. Karagiorgos (2010) explored the relationship of CSR and firms' financial performance in Greek firms. The findings showed that there was a positive correlation between SCR and firm financial performance. Saleh et al. (2011) examined the relationship between corporate social responsibility and CFP of Malaysian publicly listed companies. A longitudinal data analysis was employed over 200 firms using panel data analysis during 7 years. Results indicated a significant and positive relations between the two.

Similarly, Arshad et al. (2012) examined the effect of Islamic corporate social responsibility on corporate financial performance of 17 banks in Malaysia for the period 2008-2010. Results showed evidence that CSR activities communicated via annual reports and accounts are significantly positively related with corporate financial performance. Sun (2012) examined the association between corporate social responsibility and financial performance. The analysis revealed a significant and positive association. Also, Sarwar et al. (2012) examined the nature of relationship between corporate social responsibility and corporate financial performance in Bangladesh banks. The results revealed that financial performance is higher with higher investments in CSR. Palmer (2012) tested the impact of CSR on financial performance of S&P 500 firms for 2001-2005. Results indicated that CSR and CFP have significant positive relationship in both directions. Arsoy et al. (2012) examined the effect of CSR on FFP in an emerging economy: Turkey they investigated how corporate social responsibility affect financial performance. The results supported that an increase in CSR produces better financial performance. Uadiale and Fagbemi (2012) examined the impact of CSR activities on firm financial performance in Nigeria with a sample 40 companies. The results showed positive impact of CSR on financial performance. Gangi et al. (2012) investigated how CSR knowledge affects financial performance in 72 banks from 20 European countries over 7 years (2009-2015). CSR was found to be a positive predictor of a bank's financial performance.

Ahamed et al. (2013) examined the relationship between CSR and corporate financial performance for Malaysian firms for 5 years (2007-2011). The results indicated that there was positive and significant relationship between CSR and CFP. Pan et al. (2014) captured the effect of CSR on FFP using 228 mineral firms in China. The estimation results show a positive and significant impact. Also, Mallin et al. (2014) examined the relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance of 90 Islamic banks over 13 countries. The empirical results showed positive association between CSR and FFP. Kamatra and Kartikaningday (2015) examined the effect of CSR on financial performance for 24 companies in Chemical Industry of Indonesia. The results indicated that CSR showed significant effect on CFP. Wang et al. (2015) carried out a systematic review of the link between CSR and financial performance. They reported a positive and significant association. Furthermore, Usman et al. (2015) examined the relationship between the dimensions of CSR and corporate financial performance in Nigeria. 68 companies were used to carry out the research. The results of CSR dimensions were found to enhance corporate financial performance. Similarly, Munoz et al. (2015) examined the effect of corporate social responsibility initiatives on financial performance of 122 companies in Spain. They reported significant positive relationship.

Furthermore, Jain et al. (2016) explored the relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance in Rajasthan, India. 384 firms were used for the study and the method of analysis was structural equation modelling. The statistics showed that the overall model is fit and findings indicated a significant but a weak positive relationship between CSR and FFP. Also, Rodriguez-Fernandez (2016) investigated the bi-directional relationship between CSR and FFP in Spanish listed companies. They used 4 parts to develop an index for measuring CSR (GRI, Dow Jones Index firm inclusion, good corporate governance compliance and global compact signee). The conclusion was that social is profitable and profitable is social giving a positive impact. Yusoff and Adamu (2016) investigated the relationship between corporate social responsibility activities (environment, community, marketplace and workplace) and firm financial performance (return on assets and return on equity) of 100 Malaysian companies for a period covering 2009-2013. They reported a positive and significant relationship.

Chtourou and Triki (2017) measured the impact of CSR on financial performance. The study administered 82 questionnaires to general managers, human resource managers and CSR officers. The link was found to be positive and significant between CSR and FFP. Also, Wang and Chen (2017) examined how the US capital market received CSR by examining the impact of CSR on FFP using Dow Jones Indexed companies. The paper argued that CSR not only affect reputation but financial performance. Also, Theodoulidis et al. (2017) examined the relationship between corporate social responsibility and corporate financial performance in the tourism industries between 2005 and 2014.

The result was found to be significant and positive. Kabir and Thai (2017) investigated CSR and firm financial performance nexus. A sample of Vietnamese firms was used using two stage least squares regression. The results showed that CSR affected financial performance positively and significantly. Also, Famiyeh (2017) examined the impact of CSR on firm's financial performance in Ghana. Structural Equation Modelling was used to examine the relationship between CSR and corporate financial performance. The results demonstrated that CSR initiatives had positive relationship with firm's financial performance. Feng et al. (2017) explored how the association between a firm's engagement in CSR activities and firm financial performance related; using 17,083 firm-year observations covering 1,877 US firms over 1991 and 2011. They reported that CSR had significant positive effect.

Platonova et al. (2018) examined the relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance of Islamic banks in the Gulf Cooperation Council over the period 2000-2014. The findings of the research showed a positive significant relationship between CSR index and financial performance. Nyeadi et al. (2018) investigated empirically the impact of CSR on financial performance in South African quoted companies. The paper used panel corrected standard errors to estimate the impact of CSR on firm financial performance CSR was found to have a strong significant positive effect on FFP. However, the study failed to indicate the sector that was investigated and the population or sample that was taken. Also, Garcia-Sanchez and Martinez-Ferrero (2018) explored the role of CSR in CFP looking at the activities of CEO. Their results identified investments in CSR leads to greater FFP. Furthermore, Al-Malkawi and Javaid (2018) investigated the impact of corporate social responsibility on corporate financial performance using Zakat (Islamic arms) as a measure of CSR. The study examined a sample of 107 non-financial firms in Saudi Arabia over a ten year period (2004-2013). The results revealed that there is a strong positive relationship between CSR and CFP. Similarly, Mahrani and Soewarno (2018) interrogated the influence of good corporate social responsibility on financial performance using 102 firms in Indonesia for the period of 2014. The results showed significant positive effect.

Long et al. (2019) examined the relationship between CSR and corporate financial performance in China. Their result showed that CSR positively affects financial performance. Also, Siueia et al. (2019) examined the impact of voluntary CSR on financial performance by comparing South Africa, and Mozambique over 2012-2016 period. They reported positive significant correlation between CSR and FFP. Akben-Selcuk (2019) investigated the impact of corporate social responsibility engagement on firm financial performance in Turkey. The sample consisted of non-financial firms quoted on the Borsa Istanbul-100 index for the period 2014-2018. The results showed that corporate social responsibility had a positive relationship with financial performance. Nirino et al. (2019) investigated the impact of corporate social responsibility on firms' financial performance of 190 food and beverage companies. The research showed the positive and significant impact of CSR on firm financial performance.

Shabbir et al. (2020) examined the relationship between corporate social responsibility and corporate firm's performance in Pakistani financial and non-financial sectors they reported that there was a significant relationship between the two. In addition, Szegedi et al. (2020) examined CSR and financial performance in Pakistan using state bank and Pakistan Stock Exchange for the period 2008-2018. The methods used include content analysis and panel data techniques. The results indicated an increase in CSR led to increase in financial performance. Barauskaite and Streimikiene (2020) analyzed corporate social responsibility and financial performance of companies. The result was found to be positive between them.

Maqbool et al. (2020) investigated the relationship between CSR and FFP from bi-directional perspective. A sample of 79 companies listed on the National Stock Exchange for a period of 8 years (2008-2015) were involved. Random effects model was used to examine the link. The results show that CSR has a significant and positive nexus between CSR and FFP. Also, Fourati and Dammak (2021) explored direct and indirect effects of CSR on CFP using 3,274 firms over 2009-2016 over 25 countries. They concluded that CSR has significant and positive impact on CFP. Furthermore, Ramzan et al. (2021) examined the impact of corporate social responsibility on financial performance of banks in 20 Pakistani firms between 2008 and 2017. The results suggested that CSR had positive significant impact on FFP. Okafor et al. (2021) examined whether engaging in corporate social responsibility by tech companies can improve financial performance in US. They used 100 corporations listed on S&P-500 for the period 2017-2019. The results indicated that tech companies that spend more on CSR experienced a corresponding increase in financial performance.

Next, we review empirical literature that found significant negative relationship between corporate social responsibility and firm financial performance. For example, Crisostomo et al. (2011) examined the relationship

between corporate social responsibility and firm performance in Brazil. CSR index was developed and used to estimate the impact of CSR on financial performance. The result indicated that a negative significant relationship. Elouidani and Zoubir (2015) analyzed the influence of corporate social responsibility on financial performance of 20 firms listed on the floor of the Casablanca Stock Exchange between 2007 and 2010. They found a negative and significant impact of CSR on financial performance. Also, Furthermore, Hasan et al. (2018) examined the relationship between corporate social responsibility and corporate financial performance of S&P-500 firms in the period 2007-2011. They used return on assets, return on capital and excess stock returns to proxy financial performance and environmental, social and governance performance to proxy CSR. The results suggested that there was a linear negative significant relationship between CSR and FFP.

Lin et al. (2019) attempted to model the bi-directional links between CSR and corporate financial performance (CFP) by using both prospective and retrospective approaches. 100 companies were involved to generate 1,000 observations based on data from 2007-2016. They found a significant and negative result between the two variables. Sekhon and Kathuria (2020) analysed the impact of CSR on financial performance (return on assets, return on equity and net profit margin) in India. They used 137 companies from the CNX-500 for a period of 10 years (2008-2017) based on content analysis of CSR activities. The study found that CSR had negative significant impact on firm financial performance. Zhou et al. (2021) studied the relationship between CSR and bank financial performance in China between 2008 and 2018. The results show that CSR would had a negative significant impact on bank financial performance. However, this link become positive in the long-run.

We also review literature that failed to find any significant relationship though the direction was positive. For example, McWilliams and Siegel (2000) examined the association between CSR and financial performance by controlling for investments in research and development as a control variable. They reported insignificant impact on firm financial performance. Brine et al. (2007) examined the relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance of companies in Australia. The results revealed no statistical significant relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance. Similarly, Aras et al. (2010) investigated the relationship between corporate social responsibility and firm financial performance of companies listed on Istanbul Stock Exchange 100-Index between 2005 and 2007. They failed to find any significant relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance.

Aleksandra (2013) examined the impact of corporate social responsibility on financial performance of Polish corporations listed on the Warsaw Stock Exchange between quarter 1, 2010 and quarter 3, 2012. The research showed that participation in CSR was not statistically significant in determining financial performance in Poland. Han et al. (2016) investigated the impact of CSR on firm financial performance in South Korea They failed to find any statistically significant evidence of a relationship between CSR and FFP. Also, Liu et al. (2021) explored CSR and financial performance in Fintech technology. The paper investigated linear and non-linear relationships using return on asset and return on equity to proxy financial performance. The square value shows insignificant influence between CSR and FFP.

Finally, in the area of empirical literature, we review studies that failed to find any significant association though the direction is negative. For example, Oeyono et al. (2011) investigated whether Indonesian corporations' CSR affect their financial performance. They investigated 50 corporations using GRI and the dataset covers years 2003-2007. They reported a negative and insignificant result. Also, Hirigoyen and Poulain-Rehm (2014) examined the causal relationship between CSR and financial performance (return on equity, return on assets, market to book ratio). The study was based on a sample of 329 companies in US, Europe and Asia-Pacific for 2009-2010. Granger causality test was used to examine the relationship. The results showed that CSR does not result in better financial performance but it is negative.

In view of the fact that the major of past studies reviewed favour the link between corporate social responsibility and corporate financial performance, this article hypothesizes that:

H: Corporate social responsibility has positive and significant effects on corporate financial performance.

METHODOLOGY

The research design is correlational with a population and sample of 156 and 112, respectively. Four filters were applied: corporations must be quoted before 2012 and remain quoted in Nigeria as at the end of 2021; companies without complete 10 years annual reports were excluded, corporations that were quoted after 2021 were excluded and

companies with technical difficulties with the Exchange explained as below listing standard, missed regulatory filing, delisting in progress, delisting watch list, below listing standard and missed regulatory filing, missed regulatory filing and restricting, restructuring and below listing standard and restructuring were excluded. The total quoted corporations that were used was 112 for a period of 10 years which produces 1,120 observations. The dependent variable which is financial performance was proxy by an index derived from return on assets, earnings per share and return on equity. The independent variables: human resource development, environment, community interventions and new product research and development were used to proxy corporate social responsibility (corporate social responsibility). In the case of control variables, we tested firm size and leverage. The model used was taken from Long et al. (2019) and adjusted with two control variables.

$$FFPI_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CSRI_{i,t} + \beta_2 FSIZ_{i,t} + \beta_3 LEVG_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Where:

FFP is firm financial performance represented by an index derived from return on assets, earnings per share and return on equity (Ahamed et al., 2013; Chtourour & Triki, 2017; Jain et al., 2016; Long et al., 2019; Mallin et al., 2014; Okafor et al., 2021; Platonoa et al., 2018; Shabbir et al., 2020; Usman et al., 2015; Yahaya et al., 2015; Yahaya, 2018).

CSRI is an index derived from human resource development, environment, community and new product research and development activities (Mallin et al., 2014; Okafor et al., 2021; Platonoa et al., 2018).

FRSZ is firm size, measured by natural log of total assets (Yahaya, 2022a; 2022b).

LEV is leverage represented by proportion of debt as a fraction of equity (Yahaya & Andow, 2015).

β_0 is Constant

β_{1-3} is Beta coefficients for the 6 variables in the model.

i = Firm script ($i = 152$)

t = Time script ($t = 10$)

ε = Idiosyncrasy error term

The data were obtained from Machameratio database on all the sectors in Nigeria. They were calculated from the annual reports and accounts of the companies using financial ratios. Analysis was done using descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, regression and its diagnostics such as unusual and influential data, checking for normality of residuals, checking for homoscedasticity of residuals, checking for multicollinearity, checking for linearity, model specification and independence of model. A *priori* expectation is that corporate social responsibility is positively correlated and has significant impact on financial performance. The succeeding section is devoted for the findings of the paper.

FINDINGS

In this section, we present the results of descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, regression and its diagnostics. Table 1 consists of the results of descriptive statistics. It must be noted that descriptive statistics provide summary view of the data, detailing the number of observations, central mean, spread (volatility), minimum and maximum means.

Table 1
Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
FFPI	1120	.278	.116	.074	.6
CSRI	1120	.526	.073	.352	.688
FSIZ	1120	15.701	1.394	12.633	17.684
LEVG	1120	.456	.204	.098	1.365

Source: STATA 14 Computations

As it is easily noted, we see that the number of observations is 1,120 (112 corporations over 10 years). Firm financial performance averages 27.8 percent, with spread of 11.6 percent and lowest and highest average are 7.4 percent and 60 percent, respectively. Also, for corporate social responsibility, it averages 52.6 percent, with spread of 7.3 percent and lowest and highest average are 35.2 percent and 68.8 percent. For the two control variables; firm size averages 15.7, with a spread of 1.394 and lowest and highest averages of 12.6 and 17.7; leverage averages 45.6 percent, with a spread of 20.4 percent and lowest and highest averaging 9.8 percent and 136.5 percent. We present next the results of Pearson correlation matrix analysis.

Table 2

Correlation Matrix Results

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
(1) FFPI	1.000			
(2) CSRI	0.099* (0.001)	1.000		
(3) FSIZ	0.029 (0.335)	0.313* (0.000)	1.000	
(4) LEVG	-0.063* (0.036)	0.455* (0.000)	0.345* (0.000)	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 14 Computations

From the table, the association between corporate social responsibility (CSRI) and financial performance (FFPI) is positive (.099) and significant (.001). On the control variables, though firm size is positively related to FFP but it is not significant; while leverage is negative (-.063) but significant (.036). In Table 3, we present regression results to enable us conduct regression diagnostics in order to test whether the model used in this paper is best linear unbiased estimator.

Table 3

Ordinary Least Squares Regression

FFPI	Coef.	St.Err.	t-val	p-val	[95% Co	Interval]	Sig
CSRI	.247	.054	4.58	.000	.141	.353	***
FSIZ	.002	.003	0.93	.352	-.003	.008	
LEVG	-.082	.02	-4.19	.000	-.12	-.044	***
Constant	.146	.043	3.41	.001	.062	.23	***
Mean dependent var		0.278	SD dependent var			0.116	
R-squared		0.025	Number of obs			1120	
F-test		9.594	Prob > F			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		-1662.783	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			-1642.699	

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 14 Computations

The results in Table 3 confirm the results in Table 2. Corporate social responsibility shows positive (24.7 percent) and significant (.000) effect on corporate financial performance. It implies that for every naira spending on corporate social responsibility, financial performance improves by 24.7 percent. Although, firm size is positive (.2 percent), it is, however, insignificant (.352). Leverage is negative (-.082) but significant (.000).

Unusual and influential data have the ability to distort regression results. Figure 1 presents the state of the data in use.

Figure 1 Pictorial analysis of unusual and influential data
Source: STATA 14 Computations

Checking for normality of residuals is part of the requirements for a model to be best linear unbiased estimator. Table 4 presents results of test of normality of residual.

Table 4
Shapiro-Wilk W test for normal data

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
e	1120	0.965	24.471	7.955	0.000

Source: STATA 14 Computations

The probability-value of z is significant, that is, it is less than .05. This indicates that the test of normality of residual has failed and therefore the residual requires transformation. Table 5 presents the various available transformation options.

Table 5
Transformation Option

Transformation	formula	chi2(2)	P(chi2)
cubic	e^3	1.57	0.455
square	e^2	19.64	0.000
identity	e	57.58	0.000
square root	$\text{sqrt}(e)$.	0.000
log	$\text{log}(e)$.	0.000
1/(square root)	$1/\text{sqrt}(e)$.	0.000
inverse	$1/e$.	0.000
1/square	$1/(e^2)$.	0.000
1/cubic	$1/(e^3)$.	0.000

Source: STATA 14 Computations

The results in Table 5 clearly indicates that only the cubic root of the residual will make the residual to be normally distributed. Therefore, subsequently, this is the variable we will use to carry out further analyses. Furthermore, we check for homoscedasticity of residual and the results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6
Cameron & Trivedi's decomposition of IM-test

Source	chi2	df	p
Heteroskedasticity	125.410	9	0.000
Skewness	157.260	3	0.000
Kurtosis	13.600	1	0.000
Total	296.260	13	0.000

Source: STATA 14 Computations

The results in Table 6 indicate that the model is heteroscedastic, that is, there is presence of heteroskedasticity; this requires the use of robustness in estimating the model. Table 7 presents the results of multicollinearity test.

Table 6
Multicollinearity Test Results

	VIF	1/VIF
LEVG	1.338	.747
CSRI	1.307	.765
FSIZ	1.177	.85
Mean VIF	1.274	.

Source: STATA 14 Computations

As indicated by the results of Table 6, the variance inflation factor for all the predictors are less than 10, suggesting that the residual has no problem of multicollinearity. We further test for linearity, that is, whether the model fits into a straight line or not. The results are reported in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Linearity Test Results
Source: STATA 14 Computations

A cursory look at the 3 pictures clearly indicates that there is no major problem of non-linearity in the predictors to worry about. We also present the results of model specification test in Tables 7 and 8 because it is important to establish whether the model is properly specified or not. This is achievable by a combination of both linktest and omitted variable test.

Table 7
Results of Linktest

Source	SS	df	MS	Number	of	obs
Model	0.385	2	0.192	Prob	>	F
Residual	14.749	1117	0.013	R ²	=	0.025
Total	15.133	1119	0.014	Root	MSE	=
FFPI	Coef.	Std.Err.	t	P>t	[95%Cof.	Interval]
_hat	-0.890	3.427	-0.260	0.795	-7.614	5.834
_hatsq	3.460	6.264	0.550	0.581	-8.831	15.752
_cons	0.257	0.468	0.550	0.583	-0.661	1.175

Source: STATA 14 Computations

Table 8
Ramsey RESET test using powers of the fitted values of FFPI

Ho: model has no omitted variables

$$F(3, 1113) = 3.29$$

$$\text{Prob} > F = 0.0200$$

Source: STATA 14 Computations

While the results in Table 7 indicate absence of model specification error, the results in Table 8 clearly demonstrate otherwise. We therefore decided to shuffle the control variables (firm size and leverage) to see which model has no model specification error. Problem of model specification is solved by retaining firm size and dropping leverage. This is in line with empirical literature since most of past studies used firm size as a control variable.

Table 9
OLS Linear regression

FFPI	Coef.	St.Err.	t-val	p-val	[95% Interval]	Sig
CSRI	.037	0	327.32	.000	.037	***
FS	.000	0	-13.68	.000	0	***
Constant	.003	0	54.09	.000	.003	***
Mean dependent var		0.022	SD dependent var		0.003	
R ²		0.997	Number of obs		1120	
F-test		75640.862	Prob > F		0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		-16678.856	Bayesian crit. (BIC)		-16663.793	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Source: STATA 14 Computations

Based on the results in Table 9, we report that corporate social responsibility (CSRI) has positive and significant impact on firm financial performance (FFPI). This result is in conformity with several past studies (see Ahamed et al., 2013; Arshad et al., 2012; Chtourou & Triki, 2017; Jackson & Parsa, 2009; Jain et al., 2016; Kapoor & Sandhu, 2010; Long et al., 2019; Mallin et al., 2014; Okafor et al., 2021; Pelozo & Papania, 2008; Platonova et al., 2018; Saleh et al., 2011; Shabbir et al., 2020; Tsoutoura, 2004; Usman et al., 2015). We therefore accept the hypothesis that corporate social responsibility has positive and significant effects on corporate financial performance.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of this paper is to interrogate the impact that corporate social responsibility has on financial performance of quoted firms in Nigeria. The paper is motivated by the need for companies to complement efforts of governments and their agencies otherwise known as corporate social responsibility. Based on the findings, it is concluded that corporate social responsibility is a determinant of firm financial performance among Nigeria quoted corporations. This study also established statistically that firm size is a negative determinant of corporate financial performance. We recommend therefore that quoted corporation managers should investment more in corporate social responsibility programmes because it is good for business bottom-line. As with all empirical studies, this paper is subject to limitations. First, the choice of quoted firms in Nigeria is open to criticism as there are several non-quoted corporations in Nigeria. Second, our results may have been affected by the choice of methods. Third, relying on data from Machameratio database may not allow generalization of the findings of the study. Finally, the results may be limited by the set of variables used. Using a broad set of variables may be considered in future research.

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